

Oscillation of Even Order Nonlinear Neutral Differential Equations of E

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ABSTRACT

This paper presently exhibits about the oscillation of even order nonlinear neutral differential equations of E of the form

$$\left(e(t)z^{(n-1)}(t) \right)' + r(t)f(h(\gamma(t))) + v(t)f(\delta(t)) = 0$$

Where $z(t) = x(t) + p(t)x(\rho(t))$, $n \geq 2$, is a even integer. The output we considered $\int_{t_0}^{\infty} e^{-1}(t)dt = \infty$, and $\int_{t_0}^{\infty} e^{-1}(t)dt < \infty$. This canon here extracted enhanced and developed a few known results in literature. Some model are given to embellish our main results.

INTRODUCTION

We apprehensive with the oscillation theorems for the following half-linear even order neutral delay differential equation

$$\left(e(t)z^{(n-1)}(t) \right)' + r(t)f(h(\gamma(t))) + v(t)f(\delta(t)) = 0, t \geq t_0, \quad (1)$$

Where $z(t) = x(t) + p(t)x(\rho(t))$, $n \geq 2$, is a even integer. Every part of this paper, we assume that:

$$(E_1) e \in C([t_0, \infty), E), e(t) > 0, e'(t) \geq 0;$$

$$(E_2) p, q \in C([t_0, \infty), E),$$

$$0 \leq p(t) \leq p_0 < \infty, q(t) > 0, \text{ where } p_0 \text{ is a constant;}$$

$$(E_3) \rho \in C^1([t_0, \infty), E), \gamma \in C([t_0, \infty), E),$$

$$\delta \in C([t_0, \infty), E), \rho'(t) \geq \rho_0 > 0,$$

$$\gamma(t) \leq t, \delta(t) \leq t, \rho \circ \gamma = \gamma \circ \rho,$$

$$\rho \circ \delta = \delta \circ \rho,$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \gamma(t) = \infty, \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \delta(t) = \infty, \text{ where } \rho_0 \text{ is a constant.}$$

$$(E_4) f \in C(E, E) \text{ and}$$

$$f(x)/x \geq M_1, M_2 > 0, \text{ for } x \neq 0, \text{ where } M_1, M_2 \text{ is constant.}$$

Then the two cases are

$$\int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{e(t)} dt = \infty \quad (2)$$

$$\int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{e(t)} dt < \infty, \quad (3)$$

By a solution z of (1) a function be

$$e \in C^{m-1}([t_x, \infty), E) \text{ for some } t_z \geq t_0,$$

Where $z(t) = x(t) + a(t)x(\rho(t))$, has a property $ez^{n-1} \in C^1([t_x, \infty), E)$ and satisfies (1) on (t_z, ∞) . Then (1) satisfies $\sup\{|x|t\}: t \geq T\} > 0$ for all $T \geq t_x$ is called oscillatory.

In certain case when $n = 2$ the equation (1) lessen to the following equations

$$(e(t) (x(t) + p(t)x(\rho(t)))') + r(t)f(h(\gamma(t)) + v(t)f(\delta(t)) = 0, t \geq t_0, \tag{4}$$

Where $\int_{t_0}^x e^{-1}(t)dt = \infty,$

$$\rho(t) \leq t, \gamma(t) \leq t, \delta(t) \leq t,$$

$$0 \leq p(t) \leq p_0 < \infty.$$

Then the oscillatory behavior of the solutions of the neutral differential equations of the second order

$$(e(t) (x(t) + p(t)x(\rho(t)))') + r(t)(h(\gamma(t)) + v(t)(\delta(t)) = 0, t \geq t_0 \tag{5}$$

Where $\int_{t_0}^x e^{-1}(s)ds = \infty,$

$$0 \leq p(t) \leq p_0 < \infty.$$

The usual limitations on the coefficient of (5) be $\rho(t) \leq t, \gamma(t) \leq \rho(t), \delta(t) \leq \rho(t),$

$\gamma(t) \leq t, \delta(t) \leq t, 0 \leq p(t) < 1,$ are not assumed.

ρ Could be a advanced argument and γ, δ could be a delay argument ,

Some known expand results are seen in [1,5]. Then the

Even-order nonlinear neutral functional differential equations

$$(x(t) + p(t)x(\rho(t)))^{(n)} + r(t)f(h(\gamma(t)) + v(t)f(\delta(t)) = 0, t \geq t_0, \tag{6}$$

Where n is even $0 \leq p(t) < 1$ and $\rho(t) \leq t.$

(A) Lemma. 1

The oscillatory behavior of solutions of the following linear differential inequality

$$w'(t) + r(t)h(\gamma) + v(t)g(\delta(t)) \leq 0$$

Where $r, v, \gamma, \delta \in C([t_0, \infty)),$

$$\gamma(t)t, \delta(t) \leq t$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \gamma(t) = \infty, \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \delta(t) = \infty$$

Now integrating from $\gamma(t)$ to t and $\delta(t)$ to t

If

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \inf \int_{\gamma(t)}^t r(s)ds + \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \inf \int_{\delta(t)}^t v(s)ds > \frac{1}{e},$$

Then it has no finally positive solutions.

Main results

The main results which covenant that every solution of (1) is oscillatory

$$(1) \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \inf \int_{\gamma(t)}^t J(s)ds > \frac{1}{e}$$

$$(2) \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \sup \int_{\delta(t)}^t J(s)ds > 1$$

B.Theorem. 2.1

Assume that $\int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{e(t)} dt = \infty$ holds. If

$$\int_{t_0}^{\infty} S_1(t) + \int_{t_0}^{\infty} S_2(t) dt = \infty$$

Where $S_1(t) = \min \{r(t), r(\rho(t))\}$
 $S_2(t) = \min\{v(t), v(\rho(t))\},$ then every solutions of (1) is oscillatory.

Proof

Suppose, on the contradictory, x is a nonoscillatory solutions of (1). Without loss of generality, we may assume that there exists a constant $t_1 \geq t_0,$ such that

$$x(t) > 0, x(\rho(t)) > 0 \text{ and } (\gamma(t)) > 0,$$

$x(\delta(t)) > 0$ for all $t \geq t_1.$ Using the definitions of z and x is a eventually positive solution of (1). Then there exists $t_1 \geq t_0,$ such that

$$z(t) > 0, z'(t) > 0, z^{(n-1)}(t) > 0 \text{ and } z^n(t) \leq 0 \text{ for all } t \geq t_1.$$

$$.Hence \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} z(t) \neq 0.$$

Applying (E_4) and (1) we get

$$(e(t)z^{(n-1)}(t))' \leq -M_1 r(t)h(\gamma(t)) < 0, \quad t \geq t_1$$

$$(e(t)z^{(n-1)}(t))' \leq -M_2 v(t)g(\delta(t)) < 0, \quad t \geq t_1.$$

Therefore $(e(t)z^{(n-1)}(t))$ is a nonincreasing function. Besides, from the above inequality and the definition of $z,$ we get

Case (1)

$$\begin{aligned} & (e(t)z^{(n-1)}(t))' + M_1r(t)h(\gamma(t)) + \\ & \frac{p_0}{\rho'(t)}(e(\rho(t))z^{(n-1)}(\rho(t)))' + \\ & M_1p_0r((\rho(t))h(\gamma(\rho(t)))) \leq 0 \\ & (e(t)z^{(n-1)}(t))' + M_1R(t)z(\gamma(t)) + \\ & \frac{p_0}{\rho_0}(e(\rho(t))z^{(n-1)}(\rho(t)))' \leq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Integrating (7) from t_1 to t , we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{t_1}^t (e(s)z^{(n-1)}(s))' ds \\ & + M_1 \int_{t_1}^t R(s)z(\gamma(s)) ds \\ & + \frac{p_0}{\rho_0} \int_{t_1}^t (e(\rho(s))z^{(n-1)}(\rho(s)))' ds \\ & \leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

Pointing that $\rho'(t) \geq \rho_0 > 0$

$$\begin{aligned} & M_1 \int_{t_1}^t R(s)z(\gamma(s)) ds \leq - \int_{t_1}^t e(s)z^{(n-1)}(s))' ds \\ & - \frac{p_0}{\rho_0} \int_{t_1}^t \frac{1}{\rho'(s)} (e(\rho(s))z^{(n-1)}(\rho(s)))' ds d(\rho(s)) \\ & \leq \\ & e(t_1)z^{(n-1)}(t_1) - (e(t)z^{(n-1)}(t)) + \\ & \frac{p_0}{\rho_0^2} (e(\rho(t_1))z^{(n-1)}(\rho(t_1)) - \\ & (e(\rho(t))z^{(n-1)}(\rho(t)))) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Since $z'(t) > 0$ for $t \geq t_1$. We can find a invariable $c > 0$ such that

$$z(\gamma(t)) \geq c, t \geq t_1.$$

Then from (8) and the fact that $(e(t)z^{(n-1)}(t))$ is non increasing, we obtain

$$\int_{t_0}^{\infty} S_1(t) < \infty \quad (9)$$

Case (2)

$$\begin{aligned} & (e(t)z^{(n-1)}(t))' + M_2v(t)g(\delta(t)) \\ & + \frac{p_0}{\rho'(t)}(e(\rho(t))z^{(n-1)}(\rho(t)))' \\ & + M_2p_0v((\rho(t))g(\delta(\rho(t)))) \leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & (e(t)z^{(n-1)}(t))' + M_2V(t)z(\delta(t)) + \\ & \frac{p_0}{\rho_0}(e(\rho(t))z^{(n-1)}(\rho(t)))' \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Integrating (10) from t_1 to t , we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{t_1}^t e(s)z^{(n-1)}(s))' ds \\ & + M_2 \int_{t_1}^t V(s)z(\delta(s)) ds \\ & + \frac{p_0}{\rho_0} \int_{t_1}^t (e(\rho(s))z^{(n-1)}(\rho(s)))' ds \leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

Pointing that $\rho'(t) \geq \rho_0 > 0$

$$\begin{aligned} & M_2 \int_{t_1}^t V(s)z(\delta(s)) ds \leq - \int_{t_1}^t e(s)z^{(n-1)}(s))' ds - \\ & \frac{p_0}{\rho_0} \int_{t_1}^t \frac{1}{\rho'(s)} (e(\rho(s))z^{(n-1)}(\rho(s)))' ds d(\rho(s)) \\ & \leq \\ & (e(t_1)z^{(n-1)}(t_1) - (e(t)z^{(n-1)}(t)) + \\ & \frac{p_0}{\rho_0^2} (e(\rho(t_1))z^{(n-1)}(\rho(t_1)) - \\ & (e(\rho(t))z^{(n-1)}(\rho(t)))) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Since $z'(t) > 0$ for $t \geq t_1$. We can find a invariable $c > 0$ such that

$$z(\delta(t)) \geq c, t \geq t_1.$$

Then from (8) and the fact that $(e(t)z^{(n-1)}(t))$ is nonincreasing, we obtain $\int_{t_0}^{\infty} S_2(t) < \infty$

$$(12)$$

We get inconsistency with (9),(12).

$$\int_{t_0}^{\infty} S_1(t) + \int_{t_0}^{\infty} S_2(t) = \infty$$

Theorem. 2.2

Assume that $\int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{e(t)} dt = \infty$ holds and $\rho(t) \geq t$. if either

$$\begin{aligned} & \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \inf \left(\int_{\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\gamma^{n-1}(s)J(s)}{e(\gamma(s))} ds + \right. \\ & \left. \int_{\delta(t)}^t \frac{\delta^{n-1}(s)K(s)}{e(\delta(s))} ds \right) > \frac{(p_0 + \rho_0)(n-1)!}{\rho_0^e}, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Or when γ, δ is increasing,

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \sup \left(\int_{\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\gamma^{n-1}(s)J(s)}{e(\gamma(s))} ds + \int_{\delta(t)}^t \frac{\delta^{n-1}(s)K(s)}{e(\delta(s))} ds \right) > \frac{(p_0 + \rho_0)(n-1)!}{\rho_0}, \quad (14)$$

Where $(t) = \min\{M_1j(t), M_1j(\rho(t))\}$,

then every solution of (1) is oscillatory .

Proof

Suppose, on the contrary x is a oscillatory solution of (1). Without loss of generality, we may assume that there exists a constant $t_1 \geq t_0$, such that $x(t) > 0$,

$x(\rho(t)) > 0$ and $x(\gamma(t)) > 0$, $x(\delta(t)) > 0$ for all $t \geq t_1$.

Assume that $x^{(n)}(t)$ is not constantly zero on any interval $[t_0, \infty)$, and there exists a $t_1 > t_0$. Such that $x^{(n-1)}(t)u^{(n)}(t) \leq 0$ for all $t \geq t_1$. If $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} x(t) \neq 0$, then for every λ , $0 < \lambda < 1$, there exists $T \geq t_1$, such that for all $t \geq T$,

$$x(t) \geq \frac{\lambda}{(n-1)!} t^{n-1} u^{(n-1)}(t) \text{ forever}$$

$0 < \lambda < 1$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} (e(t)z^{(n-1)}(t))' + \frac{p_0}{\rho_0} (e(\rho(t))z^{(n-1)}(\rho(t)))' + \\ \frac{\lambda}{(n-1)!} \gamma^{n-1}(t)J(t)z^{(n-1)}(\gamma(t)) + \\ \frac{\lambda}{(n-1)!} \delta^{n-1}(t)K(t)z^{(n-1)}(\delta(t)) \leq 0, \end{aligned}$$

For every t sufficiently large.

Let $x(t) = (e(t)z^{(n-1)}(t)) > 0$. Then for all t large enough, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left(x(t) + \frac{p_0}{\rho_0} x(\rho(t)) \right)' + \\ \frac{\lambda}{(n-1)!} \frac{\gamma^{n-1}(t)J(t)}{e(\gamma(t))} x(\gamma(t)) + \\ \frac{\lambda}{(n-1)!} \frac{\delta^{n-1}(t)K(t)}{e(\delta(t))} x(\delta(t)) \leq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Next , let us denote

$y(t) = x(t) + \frac{p_0}{\rho_0} x(\rho(t))$. Since x is non increasing, it follows from $\rho(t) \geq t$ that

$$y(t) \leq \left(1 + \frac{p_0}{\rho_0} \right) x(t) . \quad (16)$$

By combining (15) and (16), we get

$$\begin{aligned} y'(t) + \frac{\rho_0}{p_0 + \rho_0} \frac{\lambda}{(n-1)!} \left(\frac{\gamma^{n-1}(t)J(t)}{e(\gamma(t))} y(\gamma(t)) + \right. \\ \left. \frac{\delta^{n-1}(t)K(t)}{e(\delta(t))} y(\delta(t)) \right) \leq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Therefore , y is a non negative solutions of (17).

Then there will be two cases

Case (1)

If

$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \inf \left(\int_{\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\gamma^{n-1}(s)J(s)}{e(\gamma(s))} ds + \int_{\delta(t)}^t \frac{\delta^{n-1}(s)K(s)}{e(\delta(s))} ds \right) > \frac{(p_0 + \rho_0)(n-1)!}{\rho_0^e}$ holds then a constant be $0 < \lambda_0 < 1$, such that

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \inf \left(\int_{\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\lambda_0}{(n-1)!} \left(\frac{\gamma^{n-1}(s)J(s)}{e(\gamma(s))} ds + \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \int_{\delta(t)}^t \frac{\delta^{n-1}(s)K(s)}{e(\delta(s))} ds \right) \right) > \frac{1}{e}, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

By lemma (1), (18) holds that (17) has negative solutions, which is contradictory.

Case (2)

By the definition of y and

$$\begin{aligned} (e(t)z^{(n-1)}(t))' + M_1R(t)z(\gamma(t)) + \\ \frac{p_0}{\rho_0} (e(\rho(t))z^{(n-1)}(\rho(t)))' \leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

we get ,

$$\begin{aligned} y'(t) = x'(t) + \frac{p_0}{\rho_0} (x(\rho(t)))' \leq -J(t)z(\gamma(t)) - \\ K(t)z(\delta(t)) < 0 \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

pointing that $\gamma(t) \leq t, \delta(t) \leq t$, there exists $t_2 \geq t_1$, such that

$$y(\gamma(t)) \geq y(t), y(\delta(t)) \geq y(t), t \geq t_2 . \quad (20)$$

Integrating (17) from $\gamma(t)$ to t and $\delta(t)$ to t and applying γ, δ is increasing, we have

$$y(t) - (y(\gamma(t)) + y(\delta(t))) + \frac{\rho_0}{p_0 + \rho_0} \frac{\lambda}{(n-1)!} \int_{\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\gamma^{n-1}(s)J(s)}{e(\gamma(s))} (y(\gamma(s)) + \int_{\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\delta^{n-1}(s)K(s)}{e(\delta(s))} y(\delta(s))) ds \leq 0, t \geq t_2 .$$

Thus

$$y(t) - (y(\gamma(t)) + y(\delta(t))) + \frac{\rho_0}{p_0 + \rho_0} \frac{\lambda}{(n-1)!} ((y(\gamma(t)) \int_{\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\gamma^{n-1}(s)J(s)}{e(\gamma(s))} + y(\delta(t)) \int_{\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\delta^{n-1}(s)K(s)}{e(\delta(s))}) ds \leq 0, t \geq t_2$$

From the above the inequality, we get

$$\frac{y(t)}{(y(\gamma(t)) + y(\delta(t)))} - 1 + \frac{\rho_0}{p_0 + \rho_0} \frac{\lambda}{(n-1)!} \int_{\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\gamma^{n-1}(s)J(s)}{e(\gamma(s))} + \int_{\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\delta^{n-1}(s)K(s)}{e(\delta(s))} ds \leq 0$$

From (20), we have

$$\frac{\rho_0}{p_0 + \rho_0} \frac{\lambda}{(n-1)!} \int_{\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\gamma^{n-1}(s)J(s)}{e(\gamma(s))} + \int_{\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\delta^{n-1}(s)K(s)}{e(\delta(s))} ds \leq 0, t \geq t_2 \tag{21}$$

Taking upper limits as $t \rightarrow \infty$ in (21) we get

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \sup (\int_{\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\gamma^{n-1}(s)J(s)}{e(\gamma(s))} ds + \int_{\delta(t)}^t \frac{\delta^{n-1}(s)K(s)}{e(\delta(s))} ds) \leq \frac{(p_0 + \rho_0)(n-1)!}{\lambda \rho_0}, \tag{22}$$

If (14) holds, we choose a constant

$0 < \lambda_0 < 1$ such that

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \sup (\int_{\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\gamma^{n-1}(s)J(s)}{e(\gamma(s))} ds + \int_{\delta(t)}^t \frac{\delta^{n-1}(s)K(s)}{e(\delta(s))} ds) > \frac{(p_0 + \rho_0)(n-1)!}{\lambda_0 \rho_0},$$

Which is in contrary with (22).

Theorem 2.3

Assume that $\int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{e(t)} dt = \infty$ holds and $\gamma(t) \leq \rho(t) \leq t, \delta(t) \leq \rho(t) \leq t$. If either

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \inf (\int_{\rho^{-1}\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\gamma^{n-1}(s)J(s)}{e(\gamma(s))} ds + \int_{\rho^{-1}\delta(t)}^t \frac{\delta^{n-1}(s)K(s)}{e(\delta(s))} ds) > \frac{(p_0 + \rho_0)(n-1)!}{\rho_0^e}, \tag{23}$$

Or when $\rho^{-1}o\gamma, \rho^{-1}o\delta$ is increasing,

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \sup (\int_{\rho^{-1}\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\gamma^{n-1}(s)J(s)}{e(\gamma(s))} ds + \int_{\rho^{-1}\delta(t)}^t \frac{\delta^{n-1}(s)K(s)}{e(\delta(s))} ds) > \frac{(p_0 + \rho_0)(n-1)!}{\rho_0} \tag{24}$$

Where J, K is defined as in theorem (2.2), then every solution of (1) is oscillatory.

Proof

Suppose, on the contrary x is a oscillatory solution of (1). Without loss of generality, we may assume that there exists a constant $t_1 \geq t_0$, such that

$$x(t) > 0, x(\rho(t)) > 0 \text{ and}$$

$(\gamma(t)) > 0, x(\delta(t)) > 0$ for all $t \geq t_1$. Continuing as in the proof of the theorem (2.2), we have

$$\left(x(t) + \frac{p_0}{\rho_0} x(\rho(t)) \right)' + \frac{\lambda}{(n-1)!} \frac{\gamma^{n-1}(t)J(t)}{e(\gamma(t))} x(\gamma(t)) + \frac{\lambda}{(n-1)!} \frac{\delta^{n-1}(t)K(t)}{e(\delta(t))} x(\delta(t)) \leq 0. \text{ Let}$$

$y(t) = x(t) + \frac{p_0}{\rho_0} x(\rho(t))$ again. Since x is non increasing, it follows from $\rho(t) \leq 0$ that

$$y(t) \leq (1 + \frac{p_0}{\rho_0})x(\rho(t)) \tag{25}$$

By combining (15) and (24), we get

$$y'(t) + \frac{\rho_0}{p_0 + \rho_0} \frac{\lambda}{(n-1)!} \left(\frac{\gamma^{n-1}(t)J(t)}{e(\gamma(t))} y(\rho^{-1}(\gamma(t))) + \frac{\delta^{n-1}(t)K(t)}{e(\delta(t))} y(\rho^{-1}(\delta(t))) \right) \leq 0 \tag{26}$$

Therefore, y is a positive solution of (26). Now, we consider the following two cases, on (23) and (24) holds.

Case (1)

If

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \inf (\int_{\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\gamma^{n-1}(s)J(s)}{e(\gamma(s))} ds + \int_{\delta(t)}^t \frac{\delta^{n-1}(s)K(s)}{e(\delta(s))} ds) > \frac{(p_0 + \rho_0)(n-1)!}{\rho_0^e} \text{ holds then a constant } 0 < \lambda_0 < 1, \text{ such that}$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \inf \left(\int_{\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\lambda_0}{(n-1)!} \left(\frac{\gamma^{n-1}(s)J(s)}{e(\gamma(s))} ds + \delta t \delta n - 1 s K s e \delta s ds \right) > 1 e \right) \quad (27)$$

Therefore (27) holds (26) has no positive solutions which is a contradiction.

Case (2)

From (19) and the condition

$\gamma(t) \leq \rho(t), \delta(t) \leq \rho(t)$, there exists

$t_2 \geq t_1$, such that $y(\rho^{-1}(\gamma(t))) \geq y(t)$,

$$y(\rho^{-1}(\delta(t))) \geq y(t) \quad t \geq t_2. \quad (28)$$

Integrating (26) from $\rho^{-1}(\gamma(t))$ to $\rho^{-1}(\delta(t))$ and applying $\rho^{-1} \circ \gamma$ is nondecreasing, then we get

$$y(t) - y(\rho^{-1}(\gamma(t))) + \frac{\rho_0}{p_0 + \rho_0} \frac{\lambda}{(n-1)!} \int_{\rho^{-1}\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\gamma^{n-1}(s)J(s)}{e(\gamma(s))} y(\rho^{-1}(\gamma(t))) + \rho - 1 \delta(t) t \delta n - 1 s K(s) e(\delta s) y \rho - 1 \delta t ds \leq 0, \quad t \geq t_2.$$

Thus

$$y(t) - y(\rho^{-1}(\gamma(t))) + \frac{\rho_0}{p_0 + \rho_0} \frac{\lambda}{(n-1)!} y(\rho^{-1}(\gamma(t))) \int_{\rho^{-1}\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\gamma^{n-1}(s)J(s)}{e(\gamma(s))} + y \rho - 1 \delta t \rho - 1 \delta(t) t \delta n - 1 s K(s) e(\delta s) ds \leq 0, \quad t \geq t_2.$$

From the inequality, we obtain

$$\frac{y(t)}{y(\rho^{-1}(\gamma(t)))} - 1 \frac{\rho_0}{p_0 + \rho_0} \frac{\lambda}{(n-1)!} \int_{\rho^{-1}\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\gamma^{n-1}(s)J(s)}{e(\gamma(s))} + \int_{\rho^{-1}\delta(t)}^t \frac{\delta^{n-1}(s)K(s)}{e(\delta(s))} ds \leq 0.$$

From (28) we get

$$\frac{\rho_0}{p_0 + \rho_0} \frac{\lambda}{(n-1)!} \int_{\rho^{-1}\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\gamma^{n-1}(s)J(s)}{e(\gamma(s))} + \rho - 1 \delta(t) t \delta n - 1 s K(s) e(\delta s) ds \leq 1, \quad t \geq t_2. \quad (29)$$

Taking the upper limit as $t \rightarrow \infty$ in (29), we get

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \sup \left(\int_{\gamma(t)}^t \frac{\gamma^{n-1}(s)J(s)}{e(\gamma(s))} ds + \delta(t) t \delta n - 1 s K(s) e(\delta s) ds \right) \leq (p_0 + \rho_0) (n-1)! \lambda \rho_0, \quad (30)$$

Then the proof is similar to that of the theorem (2.2) then it is contradiction to (24).

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